

www.bjisrd.com

Problems of Training Pedagogues and Personnel in Orphanages of Uzbekistan in 1917-1941

Eshmurodova Gulbahor Khushmurodovna

Docent of the Pedagogical Department of the University of Information Technology and Management,
Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences

***Abstract:** The article analyzes the problems of training pedagogues in orphanages in Uzbekistan in 1917-1941. The number of orphans increased sharply due to the revolution, civil war and drought of that time, the factors that led to the origin of this problem are analyzed. Also, the lack of personnel, low salaries of teachers, limited opportunities for professional development and shortcomings in the education system are discussed.*

***Key words:** orphanage, teaching staff, education, Uzbekistan, 1917-1941, problems, analysis.*

Factors such as the October Revolution of 1917 and subsequent civil war and drought led to a sharp increase in the number of orphans in Uzbekistan. Many orphanages were opened to raise and educate orphans, but there was a problem of providing them with qualified pedagogues. This article analyzes the problems of training pedagogues in Uzbekistan's orphanages in 1917-1941.

It was found necessary to think in the following directions when researching the process of teacher training:

- A. state requirements for pedagogues;
- B. provision of institutions with pedagogic personnel;
- C. material support of pedagogues of boarding schools;
- D. problems of teacher training and retraining.

When the need for pedagogues increased in the early 1930s in Tashkent, Syrdarya, Samarkand, and Fergana regions (42.36), 177 pedagogues who left the field were returned to work. The republican youth organization announced mobilization three times (1933), sent 1000 young people to pedagogic work (70,53) and mobilized them to study at pedagogic educational institutions. In the "Sturm month"

(January, 1931), 30% of city teachers were sent to the countryside. At the same time, the former employees of the National Security Agency were repressed under the name "Group of 18".

Challenges of Training Pedagogues and Personnel:

1. **Severe Shortage of Qualified Personnel.** Uzbekistan faced a dire shortage of qualified pedagogues. Many teachers lacked specialized training or sufficient experience, particularly in working with orphans, who often experienced trauma and emotional difficulties.
2. **Low Salaries and Lack of Incentives.** Pedagogues in orphanages received meager salaries, which made the profession unattractive, leading to high turnover and difficulty attracting qualified professionals.
3. **Limited Opportunities for Professional Development.** Opportunities for retraining and professional development for teachers were extremely limited. The rapid changes in the education system and the turbulent political climate created a challenging environment for pedagogical training.
4. **Orphanages Often Staffed by Other Orphans.** Many orphanages relied on older orphans, often with limited education and experience, to staff their institutions. This resulted in a cycle of inadequate training and perpetuation of the challenges within the system.
5. **Lack of Specialized Training for Orphans' Specific Needs.** Pedagogues lacked adequate training in working with children who had experienced significant trauma, loss, and instability. This hampered their ability to provide the specialized support needed by these vulnerable children.

Consequences of These Challenges

- **Subpar Quality of Education:** The lack of qualified teachers resulted in inadequate educational quality, hindering the development of orphans.
- **Emotional Neglect:** The focus on basic needs often left emotional and psychological needs of orphans unaddressed, leading to emotional and psychological issues.
- **Difficulty Integrating Back into Society:** Orphans lacked the proper skills and social support to transition into society, contributing to difficulties in finding work, building relationships, and leading stable lives.

The establishment of new school institutions was politically, economically, socially and nationally painful. It was difficult for pedagogues to teach boarding school students together with public school students, and there was a shortage of personnel.

Staffing shortages, in our opinion:

- A. political factor - refusal of old personnel to work in new schools;
- B. the fact that schools were not fully staffed even before the organizational factor-political coup (1917);
- C. insufficient funds allocated to the economic factor;
- D. the national and regional factor was caused by the lack of training of local personnel. When the state focused on solving these problems, the political factor remained a priority until the end of the researched period, and a clear political demand was placed on the pedagogues-personnel: it was necessary to protect the new regime and promote its ideas.

The fact that these requirements are incorrect was noticed as early as 1918:

- A. cadres have become propagandists of state ideology, most of them did not understand the essence of political struggle;
- B. many pedagogues, unable to adapt to the spirit of the time, left their jobs and became victims of inter-systemic struggle.

Old school teachers were recruited to fill the shortage. The only way out of this precarious situation was based on the idea of building a new system from the materials of capitalism. However, it was difficult to "train" local personnel, their re-education and immediate training of new personnel became necessary. However, the fact that these problems could not be solved in the 1920s, and conflicting views on this matter occurred, was substantiated in the research of H.M. Khalikova.

The department of children's homes under the former NSC dealt with the problem of teacher-staff training. In this process, the tasks set forth by the cultural revolution were to implement general compulsory secondary education, to promote production and scientific research. Children's homes are required to accept personnel only with the recommendation of the former National Security Council. Labor discipline has been strengthened. Educators were elected. (Tashkent, No. 7, 4.02.1920). This experience can be applied even now.

Regarding the financial support of pedagogues, the necessary measures were defined in the VIII cezd of the former regional councils (1919) and the first cezd of the heads of public education departments (1920). For example, in Samarkand region in 1921 (July-October), pedagogues left after 500,000 soums were not delivered to the department of social education.

Due to the deficit of the state budget, the Plenum of the former MIK P (July 23, 1923) decided to provide pedagogues at the expense of natural resources and public funds. In receptions, the salary was equal to the salary of institutions for children with disabilities. Sometimes, salaries were increased due to job cuts. However, pedagogues worked in difficult conditions until 1924. Often, it was necessary to open the first paths of education at the cost of one's life.

In 1924-1928, cases of not receiving salaries continued for several months. In particular, 59,601 soums were not paid out of 1,908,297 soums for 205 people in February 1924. The situation was so poor that this salary satisfied only 20-25% of the criteria for the life of pedagogues.

In 1924, the salary of educators was increased to 40 soums, and in P level boarding schools to 50-60 soums. This indicator reached 67.5 soums in the 1925/26 academic year, and 79.7 soums in the 1926/27 academic year. So, in 1917-1928, when the salary was increased by 2.2 times, when the situation did not improve, the state again determined measures to encourage pedagogues. The second prize was awarded to V. M. Lyubentsov, head of the boarding school named after K. Libknecht in Tashkent, in the "Best Rural Teacher" All-Union competition.

In 1929-1934, the salary of educators was raised to the level of school teachers (1931), one year of work experience was equaled to two calendar years (1933), (224,24). Despite this, "Poverty remains a normal situation for the people of teachers. . .", it was difficult to attract personnel to the field. For this reason, the former NSC held contests such as "The Best Children's Home of the Year" and "The Best Teacher" aimed at financial support for pedagogues. 25,000 soums were allocated from the MBK fund to reward the winners. As a result, the number of skilled pedagogues began to expand. For example, A. Ibodiev, the director of children's home No. 3 ("Dorilshafaqa") in Ko'kan city, and the music director were awarded with a cash prize of 300 soums, and the fifteenth anniversary of the institution was also held.

After the state and local budget allocations for boarding schools, father's support increased, the government allocated 500,000 soums for providing food for pedagogues. Before the 1934/35 academic year, the local leaders were tasked with providing the pedagogues of the boarding schools with land, livestock, food and industrial products, farmsteads, and auxiliary farms (11.05.1934). This year, the salary of the heads of orphanages was increased to 137 soums, and that of educators to 114 soums. As a result, the personnel who left earlier started to return to the institutions. But there were cases of non-delivery of salary funds on time. In particular, in the 1933/34 school year/ June-August/ 109.8 thousand soums were not delivered to pedagogues in the city of Tashkent, and 1 million soums were not used from the state budget allocation.

On the basis of the decision "On Ending Orphanage and Unsupervised Children" (2.06.1935), the salaries of the heads of orphanages are 181.5-250 soums, and 126.5-150 soums for educators. Forms of material protection increased: a group of pedagogues was awarded materially (300 soums) (1937). Among them were the heads of Tashkent orphanages Amirov (#8), Zaushkevich (#7), Iskhakov (#2), Ibragimov (#25), Sminova (#8), Medvedev from Namangan (#3).

Republican public organizations allocated 1,700,000 soums for these purposes. But these events were given a political tone, and it was customary to thank the state leaders for material support. At the same time, many pedagogues were repressed and sentenced to death on false charges. Among them, A. Ibodiev of Kokanlik (No. 3) (from 1936 "Mehnat Qaharmony") was arrested and shot without guilt in 1937. Rafiq Momin from Tashkent was brought to justice. In such conflicting conditions, pedagogues continued to receive additional benefits: the Regulation on Rewarding Pedagogues (1937) was adopted. The procedure for free use of holiday homes and utility services was introduced for advanced pedagogues (31.3). But looting continued in some institutions. In particular, managers embezzled up to 200,000 soums in orphanages in Bukhara (No. 1), Poyarik, and Tashkent (No. 7).

According to the decision of the Center "On increasing the salary of pedagogic employees of technical schools, adult schools and orphanages" (January 18, 1937), the heads of orphanages will receive 320-420, the teachers 256-356, and the teachers and labor supervisors will receive according to their education, work experience and the area where the institution is located. according to the salary from 230-396 soums, a new staff table was developed. However, archival documents show that the average salary in some orphanages in the republic was 185-200 soums. In order to put an end to staff leaving institutions, changes were made to their working day (26.07.1940), a new procedure was introduced to encourage pedagogues-employees of orphanages despite the hardships of the military era, and it was decided to celebrate "Teachers' Day" every year on August 30. (1940)

Local orphanages lacked dedicated staff. This situation is described in the report of the public education department of Fergana region as follows: "There are very few teachers with pure conscience. . . . they think in the old way, they are ready to go against the policy of the Soviet government. . . ". Therefore, a questionnaire (28 questions) was introduced to determine the political views of personnel. As a result, the institutions were settled by random people, mostly Europeans, who came in search of wages and shelter. For example, in the city of Tashkent (No. 15), 6 pedagogues who were not suitable according to their specialty constantly quarreled with the employees, in the boarding school No. 8 all the employees were Poles, the headmaster was a lawyer by specialty, and among the pedagogues there were graduates of the 2nd grade and ChSB (Samarkand, 1922 No. 20).

In the sources, data on the number of pedagogues of boarding schools before 1920 were added to public schools, and it does not allow to give separate indicators. In 1920, there were 1,362 pedagogic jobs in all types of boarding schools, 306 pedagogic jobs in boarding schools for normal school-age

children, and another 1,862 pedagogues. Even the existing pedagogues could not influence with their bare hands the highly disordered, mentally ill children who became nervous and sick due to chronic work with worldly orphans. If in Fergana there were 90 teachers for 1461 children, it is enough to compare that 38 people (11 pedagogues, 27 employees) corresponded to 78 orphans in the institution established by A.S. Makarenko.

In 1921, there were 1,756 school-age boarding school pedagogues, and 540 pedagogues working in normal boarding schools in 1921, which made up 27.9% of the total number of pedagogues in the country. The number of pedagogues of boarding schools was 1709-522 in 1922, and 722-380 in 1923, the number of boarding schools decreased by 14.2%.

In 1924-1928, there was little progress in terms of staffing. However, the situation is not the same everywhere, for example, in Fergana, 90% of pedagogues have an old school education, and boarding schools, which are turning into creative pedagogical laboratories, have become visible in cities. I. Sultonov, G. Rahimova, L. Rahimova, Gulsum Rahimova are live witnesses of the gathering of artists and pedagogues in the Almaiy, K.Libknecht, V.G.Chernishevskiy, S.Eshontoraeva and others will remember with pleasure experimental boarding schools in Tashkent, Zebiniso orphanage, Samarkand, Fergana, Kokand institutions.

At the same time, many advanced pedagogues lost their lives in the whirlwind of sharp political struggles during this period. For example, in "Victims of Education" in Karakalpakstan, 32 future young pedagogues were subjected to terrible torture by the Durdikilich gang. (25.08.1924). Tatar Hamza was burned alive. In Hazorasp, teacher Sofijanov was brutally killed along with his brother. At a time when education in orphanages costs 20 times more than public schools, the killing of teachers and students has become commonplace. Moreover, the ratio of personnel supply was 19:1 in Syrdarya, 25:1 in Ferghana, and 15:1 in Andijan and Kok. In order to quickly correct the situation, school graduates were sent to boarding schools. A special decision (January 18, 1927) aimed at fair distribution of personnel was adopted. As a result, there were 268 pedagogues working in orphanages in 1924, 221 in 1925, 265 in 1926, 345 in 1927, and 347 in 1928, and the actual supply ratio was 7:1.

In 1929-1934, quality and quantity indicators of personnel increased. If in 1929, 356 pedagogues worked in boarding schools, in 1930, 396, in 1931, 379, in 1932, 445, in 1933, 554, and in 1934, it reached 501 people.

Ways to solve the problem:

- Improvement of the teacher training system: In Uzbekistan, it was necessary to improve the teacher training system, to create special programs for the training of qualified teachers for orphanages.
- Increasing the salary of teaching staff: It was necessary to create an opportunity to attract qualified personnel and interest in the profession by increasing the salary of teaching staff.
- Implementation of the system of retraining and professional development of teaching staff: It was necessary to create special programs and opportunities for retraining and professional development of teaching staff.
- Studying and applying the specific features of raising orphans: It was necessary to study the specific features of raising orphans, collect data with the help of experienced pedagogues, develop and apply special educational methods.

Result

Lack of pedagogic staff and shortcomings in the education system had a negative impact on the education and upbringing of orphans. The quality of education was also low due to the low qualification of the teachers.

Summary

In the years 1917-1941, the problem of training pedagogues and personnel in Uzbekistan's orphanages was a very big problem. A lot had to be done to solve this problem. It was important to improve the system of teacher-staff training, to retrain and improve the qualifications of personnel, to study and apply specific features of raising orphans.

If in the 1920s Europeans made up 90% of the contingent of institutions, in the 1930s this figure decreased to 50-60%, and the weight of local orphans increased. However, the fate of the orphans of Stalin's repressions, eavesdropping, the Second World War, the fifties and the period of "Paratrooper Tyranny" (1980s), their educational problems await their researchers. It was understood that the future of the country depends on the training of talented, widely specialized pedagogues. Scientific and practical experiments were carried out on the territory of the communes, textbooks, manuals, didactic training tools, "pre-school institution + school-boarding school + professional-vocational school associations" were tested.

References:

1. Shohrux Nuraliyev PEDAGOG SHAXSI VA UNGA QO‘YILADIGAN TALABLAR // Scientific progress. 2021. №8.
2. Sh. Mardonov, F. Mardonov PEDAGOG KADRLAR MALAKASINI OSHIRISH TA‘LIMI // SAI. 2022. №B4.
3. Sh. Mardonov, F. Mardonov PEDAGOG KADRLAR MALAKASINI OSHIRISH TA‘LIMI // SAI. 2022. №B4.
4. Bonuxon Azizovna Umurzakova PEDAGOG FAOLIYATI VA MA‘NAVIYATINI YUKSALTIRISHDA MEDIAMADANIYAT TA‘SIRI // ReFocus. 2023. №1.
5. Rustam Safarov IXTISOSLASHTIRILGAN MAKTAB-INTERNAT XODIMLARINI BAHOLASH ORQALI SIFAT SAMARADORLIGINI ANIQLASH // SAI. 2023. №Special Issue 12.
6. Usmonova, Matluba Nosirovna IXTISOSLASHTIRILGAN MAKTAB-INTERNATLAR O‘QUVCHILARIDA MILLIY VA UMUMINSONIY FAZILATLARNI TARBİYALASHNING PEDAGOGIK IMKONIYATLARI // ORIENSS. 2022. №4.